

removed 4 DAS. Jaya gained more than Basmati 370 (see figure).

Root and shoot weight decreased with salinity and the recovery gap widened with days under stress. Salinity caused less decrease in endosperm weight due to decreased metabolic mobilization. Seed weight decreased more in Jaya than in Basmati 370 (see table).

Salinity appeared to retard root and shoot growth more on Basmati 370 than on Jaya. Recovery also was better in Jaya. High initial recovery rate in Jaya was accompanied by less dry weight decrease of endosperm, showing more hydrolysis and translocation of metabolite from endosperm. This indicated that longer stress might cause irreversible effects on metabolism. Jaya's faster recovery may be due to higher metabolic utilization from the endosperm. □

Effect of salinity on endosperm utilization rate (% seed weight decrease/5 seeds) on recovery from salt stress.^a Ludhiana, India.

Salinity (dS/m)	Day of stress removal	Variety	Endosperm utilization rate at given time (d) after germination						
			4 d	6 d	8 d	10 d	12 d	14 d	16 d
1.5	<i>Seed weight (%)</i>								
		Jaya	0.0	30.5 (30.5)	41.2 (15.3)	62.5 (36.5)	65.6 (7.8)	66.0 (2.3)	66.6 (0.6)
		Basmati 370	0.0	9.7 (9.7)	36.7 (29.9)	48.9 (19.1)	57.5 (16.8)	64.1 (15.5)	63.7 (1.2)
13.6	<i>Recovery from stress</i>								
	4	Jaya	0.0	7.5 (7.5)	24.3 (18.2)	51.6 (35.9)	59.6 (16.6)	—	—
		Basmati 370	0.0	2.5 (2.5)	22.1 (20.1)	38.7 (21.3)	51.1 (20.1)	—	—
	6	Jaya	—	0.0	11.3 (11.3)	25.4 (15.8)	48.3 (30.6)	62.2 (27.2)	—
		Basmati 370	—	0.0	13.0 (13.0)	25.1 (13.9)	38.9 (18.9)	47.7 (14.4)	—
	8	Jaya	—	—	0.0	19.5 (19.5)	29.8 (12.8)	39.0 (13.1)	59.7 (33.9)
	Basmati 370	—	—	0.0	8.3 (8.3)	20.1 (12.9)	34.2 (17.6)	45.3 (16.9)	

^a Values in parentheses indicate increase over time interval.

Effect of salinity on net assimilation and rice grain yield

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We studied the critical limits of salt tolerance and the effects of salinity on net assimilation rate (NAR) of M1-48, Jaya, CST-202-2, CST-438-1, CST-14-2, CST-100-1, and CSR-1 rice varieties. M1-48 and CSR-1 were the salt-sensitive and salt-tolerant checks. Jaya and the CST genotypes have been found promising in coastal saline soils.

Three salinity levels — ECe 4.0, 8.0, and 12.0 dS/m — were created artificially by adding saline river water. At 25 °C, average composition of river water at 35 dS/m was 7571.3 Na, 269.2 K, 403.8 Ca, 778.0 Mg, 1314.3 Cl, 969.1 ppm SO₄, and pH 7.8.

Thirty-day-old seedlings were transplanted in 20-kg capacity porcelain pots, 4 plants/pot, with 4 replications. Fertilizer was applied at 120 kg N, 26.4 kg P, 49.8 kg K/ha as urea, single superphosphate, and muriate of potash.

Effect of salinity levels (3, 8, 12 dS/m) on grain yield and NAR of 7 varieties. Parganas, India.

Variety	Grain yield (g/plant)			NAR at peak tillering (g/plant per wk)		
	3.0	8.0	12.0	3.0	8.0	12.0
M1-48	17.1	10.3	Nil	3.24	0.51	0.06
Jaya	14.4	12.3	11.7	3.08	1.55	1.08
CST-202-2	32.6	21.8	10.7	1.47	1.01	0.16
CST-438-1	22.1	20.7	8.7	3.04	0.60	0.08
CST-14-2	28.5	23.3	15.2	3.24	2.10	1.80
CST-100-1	21.6	21.6	9.6	1.81	1.36	0.76
CSR-1	31.8	29.5	13.0	1.81	2.00	1.09
CD at P = 0.05						
	Varieties: 2.67			0.13		
	Salinity: 1.74			0.08		
	Var. × Sal: 4.62			0.22		

CST-14-2 had the highest grain yield at ECe 12 dS/m, followed by CSR-1 (see table). At peak tillering, NAR was significantly reduced in all genotypes

with increase in soil salinity. This reduction was least in CST-14-2. CST-14-2 and CSR-1 are the more tolerant of the genotypes tested. □

Integrated germplasm improvement

Improved rice varieties released in Nigeria

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Five NCRI breeding lines belonging to three crosses (Table 1) were recently released as FARO 30 to 34. Three medium-duration ITA lines were released as FARO 35 to 37. The

Table 1. Pedigree, parentage, and agronomic characters of 8 lowland rice varieties newly released in Nigeria.

Variety	Pedigree	Parentage	Ht (cm)	Maturity (d)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Reaction ^a to		
						Bl	Fe toxicity	RYMV
<i>Early duration</i>								
FARO 30	FAROX 228-2-1-1	FARO 15/IR28	105	115	194	R	MR	MR
FARO 31	FAROX 228-3-1-1	FARO 15/IR28	104	118	258	R	MR	MR
FARO 32	FAROX 228-4-1-1	FARO 15/IR28	91	117	221	MR	MR	MR
FARO 33	FAROX 233-1-1-1	FARO 12/IR28	100	115	259	R	S	MR
FARO 34	FAROX 239-2-1-1	IR28/FARO 12	90	115	209	R	MR	MR
FARO 27 (check)	TOx 103	—	91	119	253	MR	MR	MR
<i>Medium duration</i>								
FARO 35	ITA 212	BG90-2 ⁴ /Tetep	97	132	210	R	S	MR
FARO 36	ITA 222	Mahsuri/IET1444	91	127	227	R	MR	MR
FARO 37	ITA 306	TOx 494-3696/ TOx 711//BG6812	105	124	203	R	MR	MR
FARO 29 (check)	BG90-2	—	97	130	216	S	MR	MR

^a S = susceptible, R = resistant, MR = moderately resistant.

varieties were tested in zonal and multilocation trials.

All the varieties exhibit high yield potential. They are resistant to blast (Bl) and moderately resistant to rice yellow mottle virus (RYMV) (diseases common in the irrigated lowland ecology). In the early-duration group, FARO 30 had the highest yield (6.5 t/ha), with very good cooking quality (Table 2). FARO 34 combines long slender grains, a character highly preferred by Nigerian consumers, with very good milling and cooking qualities.

The medium-duration FARO 37 possesses high yield and long slender grains.

FARO 33 and 35 are susceptible to Fe

Table 2. Grain yields and grain qualities of 8 lowland rice varieties newly released in Nigeria.

Variety	Grain yield ^a (t/ha)	Grain type	Cooking quality	Amylose group ^b
<i>Early duration</i>				
FARO 30	6.5	Medium bold	Very good	Intermediate
FARO 31	5.0	Medium bold	Good	Intermediate
FARO 32	5.3	Medium bold	Good	Intermediate
FARO 33	5.8	Long slender	Good	Intermediate
FARO 34	5.0	Long slender	Very good	Intermediate
FARO 27 (check)	4.9	Medium bold	Good	High
<i>Medium duration</i>				
FARO 35	5.6	Medium bold	Good	High
FARO 36	6.3	Medium bold	Good	High
FARO 37	5.8	Long slender	Good	High
FARO 29 (check)	5.6	Medium bold	Good	High

^a Av of 3 yr (1984-86) multilocation trials. ^b Intermediate = 20-25%, high = above 25%.

toxicity, the others are moderately resistant.

All early-maturing varieties have

intermediate amylose; the medium-maturing have high amylose. □

High-yielding, medium-duration variety for Tamil Nadu

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Performance of ACM31, a promising, medium-duration culture at ACRI, Madurai, Tamil Nadu, India, 1984-85 to 1986-87.

Variety	Mean yield ^a (t/ha)	Days to 50% flowering	Plant height (cm)	Panicle length (cm)	Panicles (no./hill)
ACM31	6.2	92	95.6	20.6	10.4
IR20	4.7	96	101.8	22.8	13.6

^a For 3 yr.

ACM31, a high-yielding, medium-duration (132 d) variety, is a cross derivative of CO 13 and IR26. The culture is semidwarf and nonlodging with medium slender white grains. Its performance was evaluated for 3 yr 1984-85 to 1986-87 (see table). Mean grain yield was 6.2 t/ha, 31.9% more

than IR20. This variety could replace IR20 in the Periyar-Vaigai River ayacut area. □

Promising, long-duration rice variety for Kanyakumari District, Tamil Nadu

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Traditional rice varieties are grown in about 40% (9,200 ha) of the rice area in